

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On Radio k -Chromatic Number of Various Graphs

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Abstract

Objective: The main objective of the study is to reduce radio spectrums without any interference. This study aims to find the smallest span of radio k chromatic number of various graphs. The minimal number of colors essential to color a graph is called its span. **Methods:** In this paper, we address the issue of minimizing interference by modeling it as a radio k -coloring problem on graphs, when vertices and the connections between them represent the spectrum bandwidth indicated by edges. For a positive integer k , a radio k – coloring of simply connected graph T , is a function $\phi: V(T) \rightarrow \{c_0, c_1, c_2, \dots\}$ such that $|\phi(u) - \phi(v)| \geq 1 + k - d(u, v)$ for each pair of distinct vertices u and v of T , when $d(u, v)$ is the distance between u and v in T . The maximum color granted by ϕ is called span, which can be denoted by $rc_k(\phi)$. The radio k – chromatic number $rc_k(T)$ of T is the minimal $\{rc_k(\phi)\}$, when ϕ is a radio k – coloring of T . **Findings:** This study presents the exact value of the radio k -chromatic number of some graphs like $T_n, TC_n, A(T_n), U_{n, n-1}$ for $2 \leq k \leq \text{diam}(T)$, when $\text{diam}(T)$ is the diameter of graph T . **Novelty:** By introducing an interference graph, the channel assigned gets transformed into a graph coloring issue, eventually confronting the channel assigned problem for radio spectrum.

Keywords: Radio k – Chromatic Number; Triangular Snake Graph; Triangular Cactus Graph; Alternative Triangular Snake Graph; Umbrella Graph

1 Introduction

Graph coloring is the technique of allocation of colors to each vertex of a graph T such that non-adjacent vertices get a uniform color. The main intent is to reduce the number of colors while coloring a graph T . The minimal number of colors essential to color a graph T is called its chromatic number of that graph T . Motivated by channel assigned problem, Chartand et al. ⁽¹⁾ introduced radio k -coloring of graphs. For any graph T we denote the set of vertices $V(T)$ and set of edges $E(T)$ of T respectively. The distance $d(u, v)$ between two vertices u and v of a graph, T is the length (number of edges) of the shortest path connecting u and v . The diameter $\text{diam}(T)$ of a graph, T is the maximum $d(u, v)$ taken over every pair of vertices u, v of T . For any positive integer $1 \leq k \leq \text{diam}(T)$, radio

k – coloring of T is a function $\phi: V(T) \rightarrow \{C_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ satisfying the condition $|\phi(u) - \phi(v)| \geq 1 + k - d(u,v)$, for all distinct $u, v \in V(T)$. The radio k – chromatic number $rc_k(T)$ of T is the minimum $rc_k(\phi)$. The radio antipodal number, denoted by $an(T)$, is the minimum span of a radio($diam(T)-1$) coloring of T and the radio number, denoted by $rn(T)$, is the minimum span of a radio $diam(T)$ coloring of T. concentrate on finding a lower bound of $rc_k(T)$. Orden, and Gimenez⁽²⁾ give the Spectrum Graph Coloring and Applications to Wi-Fi Channel Assigned. Nirajan and Srinivasa Rao Kola⁽³⁾ discussed the radio k-chromatic number of paths. The upper bound for radio k chromatic number was determined by the authors Laxman Saha,⁽⁴⁾ and Elsayed, Badr⁽⁵⁾. The lower bound for radio k chromatic number was discussed by the authors Sandip Das, Sasthi⁽⁶⁾, and Nirajan and Srinivasa Rao Kola⁽⁷⁾. In this paper, we determine the radio k-chromatic number for various graphs for any integer $2 \leq k \leq diam(T)$. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In section 2, some of the preliminary results and bounds are given briefly. In section 3, the radio k – chromatic number for various graphs for any integer $2 \leq k \leq diam(T)$. Finally, section 4 concludes the paper.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 1.⁽⁷⁾ For any graph T we denote the set of vertices $V(T)$ and set of edges $E(T)$ of T respectively. The distance $d(u,v)$ between two vertices u and v of a graph, T is the length (number of edges) of the shortest path connecting u and v. The diameter $diam(T)$ of a graph, T is the maximum $d(u,v)$ taken over every pair of vertices u,v of T. For any positive integer $1 \leq k \leq diam(T)$, radio k-coloring of T is a function $\phi: V(T) \rightarrow \{C_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ satisfying the condition $|\phi(u) - \phi(v)| \geq 1 + k - d(u,v)$, for all distinct $u,v \in V(T)$. The radio k- chromatic number $rc_k(T)$ of T is the minimum $rc_k(\phi)$.

Lemma 2.⁽⁷⁾ For any graph T and $1 \leq k \leq diam(T)$, we have

$$rc_k(G) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

Definition 3.⁽⁸⁾ A triangular snake graph T_n is obtained from a path s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n by joining s_i and s_{i+1} to a new vertex t_i for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. That is, every edge of the path is replaced by a triangle C_3 .

Definition 4.⁽⁸⁾ A triangular cactus TC_n is a linked graph that only consists of triangles a sits building blocks.

Definition 5.⁽⁸⁾ An alternate triangular snake $A(T_n)$ is obtained from a path u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n by joining u_i and u_{i+1} (alternately) to a new vertex v_i . That is every alternate edge of path is replaced by C_3 .

Definition 6.⁽⁹⁾ An umbrella graph $U_{n, n-1}$ is a graph that is formed by combining a path graph and the center vertex of a fan graph. The number of vertices in an umbrella graph is $m+n$ and the number of edges is $2m+n-2$.

3 Results and Discussion

In this section, we determine the radio k- chromatic number for various graphs such that Triangular Snake Graph T_n , Triangular Cactus Graph TC_n , Alternative Triangular Snake Graph $A(T_n)$, Umbrella Graph $U_{n, n-1}$ for any integer $2 \leq k \leq diam(T)$.

Theorem 3.1

For any positive integer $n \geq 3$ and $2 \leq k \leq diam(T_n)$ then

$$rc_k(T_n) = \begin{cases} 6; & n = 3 \\ 5k - 3; & n \geq 4 \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let the vertex set and edge set of triangular snake graph is defined by $V(T_n) = \{v_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i: 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ and $E(T_n) = \{v_i v_{i+1}: 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_i u_i: 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_{i+1} u_i: 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with $|V(T_n)| = 2n-1$, $|E(T_n)| = 3n-3$ and $diam(T_n) = n-1$

Case 1: when n = 3

From Lemma 2, it is observed that $rc_k(T_n) \geq |D_2| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i) + 1$, we have $rc_k(T_n) \geq 6$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(T_n) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_6\}$, assign the colors for $V(T_n)$ as follows;

$\phi(v_1) = C_0, \phi(v_2) = C_2, \phi(v_3) = C_4, \phi(u_1) = C_5, \phi(u_2) = C_6$ the condition of radio k-coloring, we have $rc_k(T_n) \leq 6$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(v_2)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, v_2)$$

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(u_1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, u_1)$$

$$|\phi(v_2) - \phi(u_1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_2, u_1)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition. Therefore, we get $rc_k(T_n) = 6$

Case 2: when $n \geq 4$

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(T_n) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

We have $rc_k(TS_n) \geq 5k - 3$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(T_n) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{5k-3}\}$, assign the colors for $V(T_n)$ as follows;

$$\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) = \begin{cases} 5k-3; & i = 0(mod\ 3) \\ 3k-1; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \\ 4k-2; & i = 2(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

$$\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod\ 3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring, we have $(T) \leq 5k - 3$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) \\ |\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) \\ |\phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) \end{aligned}$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(T_n) = 5k - 3$

Theorem 3.2

For any positive integer $n \geq 3$ and $2 \leq k \leq \text{diam}(TC_n)$ then

$$rc_k(TC_n) = \begin{cases} nk - (n-2); & n = 3, 4 \\ 5k - 3; & n \geq 5 \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let the vertex set and edge set of triangular cactus graph is defined by $V(TC_n) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\}$ and $E(TC_n) = \{v_i v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_i u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \cup \{v_{i+1} u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\}$ with $|V(TC_n)| = 2n-2$, $|E(TC_n)| = 3n-5$ and $\text{diam}(TC_n) = n-1$

Case 1: when $n=3$ and 4

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(T_n) \geq \begin{cases} |D_3| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i); & \text{if } k = 3 \\ |D_2| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2 \end{cases}$$

We have $rc_k(TC_n) \geq nk - (n-2)$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(TC_n) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{nk-(n-2)}\}$, assign the colors for $V(TC_n)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(u_1) &= C_{nk-(n-3)} & \phi(v_1) &= \phi(v_4) = C_0 \\ \phi(u_2) &= C_{nk-(n-2)} & \phi(v_2) &= C_k & \phi(v_3) &= C_{2k} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. So, we have $rc_k(TC_n) \leq nk - (n-2)$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) \\ |\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2) \\ |\phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)| &\geq 1 + k - d(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2) \end{aligned}$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(TC_n) = nk - (n-2)$

Case 2: when $n \geq 5$

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(TC_n) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

We have $rc_k(TC_n) \geq 5k - 3$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(TC_n) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{5k-3}\}$, assign the colors for $V(TC_n)$ as follows;

$$\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2) = \begin{cases} 5k-3; & i = 0(mod\ 3) \\ 3k-1; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \\ 4k-2; & i = 2(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

$$\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod\ 3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring, we have $rc_k(TC_n) \geq 5k - 3$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)$$

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)$$

$$|\phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(TC_n) = 5k - 3$

Theorem 3.3

For any positive integer $n \geq 4$ and $2 \leq k \leq \text{diam}(A(T_n))$ then

$$rc_k(A(T_n)) = \begin{cases} 6; & k = 2 \\ 5k - 5; & 3 \leq k \leq \text{diam}(A(T_n)) \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let the vertex of alternative triangular snake graph is defined by $V(A(T_n)) = \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor\}$ and $|V(A(T_n))| = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + n$ with $\text{diam}(A(T_n)) = n-1$

Case 1: when $k=2$

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(A(TC_n)) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

We that $rc_k(A(T_n)) \geq 6$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(A(T_n)) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_6\}$, assign the colors for $V(A(T_n))$ as follows;

$$\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod\ 3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

$$\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor) = \begin{cases} 5; & i = 0, 2(mod\ 3) \\ 6; & i = 1(mod\ 3) \end{cases}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. So, we have that $rc_k(A(T_n)) \leq 6$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(v_2)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, v_2)$$

$$|\phi(v_2) - \phi(v_3)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_2, v_3)$$

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(u_1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, u_1)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition. Therefore, we get $rc_k(A(T_n))=6$. From Lemma 2, it is observed that

Case 2: when $3 \leq k \leq diam(A(T_n))$

$$rc_k(A(T_n)) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

We have that $rc_k(A(T_n)) \geq 5k - 5$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(A(T_n)) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{5k-5}\}$, assign the colors for $V(A(T_n))$ as follows;

$$\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod3) \end{cases}$$

$\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor) = C_{(2k+1)+(k-2)i}$ when $1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. We have $(A(T)) \leq 5k - 5$.

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| \geq 1 + k - d(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)$$

$$|\phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-2) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-2, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n)$$

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n/2) - \phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n/2, u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(AT_n)=5k - 5$

Theorem 3.4

For any positive integer $n \geq 3$ and $2 \leq k \leq diam(U_{n,n-1})$ then

$$rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) = \begin{cases} 6; & n = 3 \\ (n+1)k - (n-1); & n = 4 \\ (k-1)n + k; & n \geq 5 \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let the vertex set and edge set of umbrella graph is defined by $V(U_{n,n-1}) = \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ and $E(U_{n,n-1}) = \{u_i u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_i v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \cup \{v_1 u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ with $|V(U_{n,n-1})| = 2n-1$, $|E(U_{n,n-1})| = 3n-3$ and $diam(U_{n,n-1}) = n-1$.

Case 1: When n=3

From Lemma 2, it is observed that $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \geq |D_2| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i) + 1$, we have $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \geq 6$

Consider the coloring function $\phi: V(U_{n,n-1}) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_6\}$, assign the colors for the vertices of $(U_{n,n-1})$ as follows;

$$\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod3) \end{cases}$$

$$\phi(u_2) = C_6 \quad \phi(u_{2i-1}) = C_{k+i} \quad \text{when } 1 \leq i \leq n$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. So, we have that $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \leq 6$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(u_1) - \phi(u_2)| \geq 1 + k - d(u_1, u_2)$$

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(u_1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, u_1)$$

$$|\phi(v_1) - \phi(v_2)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_1, v_2)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) = 6$

Case 2 : When n=4

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(A(T_n)) \geq \begin{cases} |D_2| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i); & \text{if } k = 3 \\ |D_2| - 2 + 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 L_i(1-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2 \end{cases}$$

We have $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \geq (n+1)k-(n-1)$

Consider the coloring function $\phi:V(U_{n,n-1}) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{(n+1)k-(n-1)}\}$, assign the colors for the vertices of $(U_{n,n-1})$ as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(v_1) &= C_0 & \phi(u_1) &= C_{2k-1} \\ \phi(v_2) &= C_2 & \phi(u_2) &= C_{4k-2} \\ \phi(v_3) &= C_4 & \phi(u_3) &= C_{3k-2} \\ \phi(u_4) &= C_{5k-3} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. So, we have that $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \leq (n+1)k-(n-1)$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(u_2) - \phi(u_3)| \geq 1 + k - d(u_2, u_3)$$

$$|\phi(u_3) - \phi(u_4)| \geq 1 + k - d(u_3, u_4)$$

$$|\phi(v_2) - \phi(v_3)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_2, v_3)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) = (n+1)k-(n-1)$

Case 3: When $n \geq 5$

From Lemma 2, it is observed that

$$rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \geq \begin{cases} |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i); & \text{if } k = 2p + 1 \\ |D_k| - 2p + 2 \sum_{i=0}^p L_i(p-i) + 1; & \text{if } k = 2p \end{cases}$$

We have $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \geq (k-1)n + k$

Consider the coloring function $\phi:V(U_{n,n-1}) \rightarrow \{C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{(k-1)n+k}\}$, assign the colors for the vertices of $(U_{n,n-1})$ as follows;

$$\phi(u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) = \begin{cases} 2k; & i = 0(mod3) \\ 0; & i = 1(mod3) \\ k; & i = 2(mod3) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(u_{2i-1}) &= C_{k+(k-1)i} & \text{when } 1 \leq i \leq \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil \\ \phi(u_{2i}) &= C_{(k-1)\lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil + k+(k-1)i} & \text{when } 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the above assigned colors satisfy the condition of radio k-coloring. So, we have that $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) \leq (k-1)n+k$

Now let us apply the condition of radio k-coloring to the following pairs of vertices.

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)$$

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)$$

$$|\phi(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n) - \phi(u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)| \geq 1 + k - d(v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n, u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1)$$

By a similar procedure, it can be verified that the remaining pair of nodes satisfies the radio k-coloring condition.

Therefore, we get $rc_k(U_{n,n-1}) = (k-1)n+k$

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we attain the exact value of the radio k- chromatic number for $T_n, TC_n, A(T_n), U_{n,n-1}$. Despite the few results in radio k-coloring we still experiment on radio k-chromatic numbers of various families of graphs.

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